

Speculation on an Example of Maximization of Tsallis Entropy Subject to a Constraint

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In this note, we try to provide a physical example associated with Tsallis entropy subject to two a priori constraints and yields, upon maximization, the usual Tsallis \exp_q distribution. This example is based on a notion of a seed which may either germinate with a probability f or mildew with a probability $1-f$. If the seed mildews, it must be washed and dried and one must try again. A main idea, however, is that on average, the seed develops a resistance to mildew after q tries. Thus, f^q represents the probability that the seed germinates on average.

The next assumption is that a seed receives a certain amount of sunlight/rain and that this governs the amount of fruit it produces, i.e. e_i , but that it also governs the germination rate, so one has $f(e_i)$. This justifies the first constraint: $\sum_i f(e_i) = 1$. By taking away some sunlight/rain from one seed, its $f(e_i)$ is reduced, but another $f(e_i)$ is augmented because it receives extra sunlight/rain. Given a total amount of sunlight/rain, one might suggest that there is a second a priori constraint of a production of E fruit.

The next key assumption is that to germinate, on average q tries are required, regardless of e_i (i.e. the amount of fruit produced which is tied to the amount of sunlight/rain). Thus, $f(e_i)^q$ is the probability that a seed (with sunlight/rain conditions linked to e_i) will germinate (and hence produce e_i of fruit). A physical picture associated with this is that after q tries, on average, the seed gains resistance to mildew. Thus, the probabilistic picture is somewhat complicated, but modeled in a simple way.

The idea of maximization of entropy subject to a priori constraints seems to mean that one finds a quantity (called entropy) which maximizes the lack of any special knowledge. In practice, if one wants to know about the position of a particle in a box, removing all knowledge (maximizing ignorance) means no part of the box is special. In other words, one maximizes the failure of finding the particle by stating that it may be in any region of the box with the same probability (because there is no extra information suggesting one should check one part of the box first versus another). In the seed scenario here, we argue that one should maximize the failure of a seed to germinate in q tries (in analogy) and so such an expression would be: $1 - \sum_i f(e_i)^q$. This number is guaranteed to be less than 1. This approach then yields, upon maximization of this failure expression subject to the two a priori constraints, the Tsallis \exp_q distribution for $q > 1$. The $q=1$ is a special case, but follows the same physical arguments, we suggest.

The Notion of Removal of Information

It seems that statistical mechanics (at least the Maxwell-Boltzmann scenario) involves removing as much special information as possible. In other words, there exist some a priori constraints which represent the only special information present. For everything else, one tries to impose as much ignorance as possible. As an example, given a box of volume V , the maximum ignorance would be to indicate one has no idea of the location of the particle. Any preference for a particular position in the box indicates extra information, hence not maximum ignorance. The point we wish to make is that in this case volume V is a measure of the

maximum ignorance, i.e. the failure to find the particle. We relate maximum ignorance to failure (related to the probability in question). This, we argue, is important for developing the notion of Tsallis entropy.

The Notion of a Probability which must Occur in an AND Scenario with q Factors

Single probabilities $f(e_i)$ are common, but classical probability theory allows for AND and OR situations. An AND situation involves multiple tests. We argue that there may be physical scenarios which require multiple tests until a success occurs. In principle, this implies that the probabilistic process is complicated. In the case of a die or coin toss, it is not. One simply tosses the coin to see what occurs. In the case of planting a seed, however, there may be a certain probability that it germinates or does not in a certain trial. If it does not germinate, perhaps due to mildew, one may remove the seed, dry it, and try again at a later time. We suggest that it might require a model in which an average of q trials are needed, i.e. $f(e_i)$ power q is the probability for it to germinate. After q trials, the seed develops resistance to mildew and so one does not have the scenario of mildew extending beyond an average of q .

This scenario suggests then that there is not only the probability for mildew to occur, but that another physical process is occurring, namely a mildew resistant switch may turn on. Thus, the $f(e_i)$ power q scenario refers to more complicated probabilistic scenarios than simply an independent success failure with nothing else occurring. For $f(e_i)$ power q , there is a set of q independent success-failure scenarios in an AND picture, but in general this product of AND factors should continue beyond q unless something else is occurring (and this also may be of a statistical nature, but may be approximated by q). One must try to germinate it q times on average before there is success. Thus, the Maxwell-Boltzmann expression for two body scattering;

$$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((1)),$$

which suggests that the presence of a particle guarantees an interaction, is not the general case. This is already known from the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein examples. Here we simply consider an AND situation with a fixed q as representing certain physical scenarios in which multiple tries are required.

$f(e_i)$ i.e. Probability Linked to an Extensive Parameter e_i

In the above section, we described a seed which may mildew and not germinate (until one cleans it and tries again), but there was no notion of any extensive quantity e_i . We suggest that if a seed germinates, it produces e_i amount of fruit. The question then is: What does e_i have to do with f which is the probability for a seed to germinate in one try (out of an average q tries)? We propose the following scenario. If one imagines that a certain amount of total sunlight/rain is available, then these natural resources may be partitioned among different seeds. In such a case, there may be a certain amount of produce e_i which is also linked to $f(e_i)$. If a seed receives a certain amount of sunlight/rain it has both a certain probability to germinate per try

due to this sunlight/rain and if it does germinate, it produces e_i amount of fruit. In such a case, $f(e_i)$ is justified.

Next, we assume that there is a certain amount of sunlight/rain available which may be partitioned among the seeds. This, we argue, justifies:

$$\sum_i f(e_i) = 1 \quad ((2))$$

Furthermore, one may introduce a second a priori constraint, namely that given a certain number of seeds N and a certain amount of sunlight/rain, one expects a fixed amount produced. In such a case, one has:

$$\sum_i e_i f(e_i)^q = E \text{ fixed amount} \quad ((3))$$

Here $f(e_i)$ is the germination rate for each try (with q being required on average) before one germination occurs which produces e_i of fruit.

Maximum Uncertainty

Entropy is described as the quantification of the amount of uncertainty in a system. We argue that it is linked to the notion of maximizing ignorance or failure. In particular, if one has a volume V , the scenario of maximum ignorance is one in which one does not know the location of a particle. This is equivalent to maximizing the failure to find the particle. We suggest that this notion of failure is important because it allows one to write the following Failure expression for the seed scenario:

$$1 - \sum_i f(e_i)^q \quad ((4))$$

We note that given ((2)), the sum expression in ((4)) must be <1 for $q > 1$. We consider the case of $q=1$ separately. Thus, it seems that one should maximize the amount of failure ((4)) subject to the two a priori constraints ((2)) and ((3)) i.e.

$$q f(e_i)^{q-1} - b_1 - b_2 e_i^q f(e_i)^{q-1} = 0 \quad \text{for each } df(e_i) \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{or } C f(e_i) = \{1 - b_2 q e_i\}^{1/(1-q)} \quad ((6))$$

where $C = \{b_1/q\}^{1/1-q}$. Now b_1 and b_2 and Lagrange multipliers which may be adjusted even before one uses $f(e_i)$ in ((6)) in the constraint equations. In particular, one may make adjustments for the $q=1$ case in which ((4)) is 0, even though this case should be associated with a solution linked to the Maxwell-Boltzmann result in which only one $f(e_i)$ try is required for successful germination. One may then modify ((6)) to:

$$f(e_i) = \{1 - (1-q) e_i/T\}^{1/(1-q)} \quad ((7))$$

$f(e_i)$ is then the usual Tsallis \exp_q result which becomes the Maxwell-Boltzmann \exp for the $q=1$ case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to provide a physical example for writing a Tsallis entropy with two constraints and maximizing it. We consider the example of a seed which has a probability to germinate in a single planting of f and $1-f$ to mildew. If it mildews, the seed needs to be washed and dried and planted again. Even though this seems like a possibly endless process, there may be other physical factors which suggest that a seed, on average, cannot mildew more than q times because it develops a resistance by that time. In other words, there is not simply the probability of mildew or not, but other physical factors occur which affect the overall probabilistic value f power q .

The next key idea is to assume that the probability to mildew is not simply a fixed number f , but is linked to the sunlight/rain the seed receives and these same resources govern the amount of fruit e_i it produces if it germinates. In such a case, one has $f(e_i)$. If there is a fixed amount of sunlight/rain, then one may introduce two constraints. The first is that: $\sum f(e_i)=1$ because removing some sunlight/rain from one seed (linked with e_i) changes its mildew rate in such a way that this is compensated by changes in other $f(e_i)$ rates. Secondly, an overall amount of sunlight/rain is expected to produce E amount of total fruit for N seeds, so $E=\sum e_i f(e_i)^q$.

The next consolidation is to suggest one seeks a distribution $f(e_i)$ linked with maximum ignorance. This, we argue, means finding the maximum failure probability: $1-\sum f(e_i)^q$ which is <1 for $q>1$. Maximizing this value subject to the two a priori constraints leads to an expression very similar to the Tsallis \exp_q function. If one insists that the $q=1$ case match the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, one finally arrives at the full Tsallis \exp_q function.